

Coordination Compounds of Cu(I) with Substituted Thioureas

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Cuprous chloride forms complexes with diphenyl thiourea, diisopropyl thiourea, naphthyl thiourea (1:2), allyl thiourea, benzyl thiourea hydro chloride and *o*-tolyl thiourea (1:1). Infra red spectra of Cu (I) complexes have been studied in the region 5.0 to 15.0 μ . From the studies it is concluded that Cu (I) coordinates through sulphur in all cases except that of allyl thiourea. In the latter it appears that there is coordination through nitrogen.

In recent years, infra red spectra of a number of metal thiourea complexes have been investigated.¹⁻⁴ These studies are mainly based on Kumler and Fohler's⁵ resonance structure for thiourea with 20-30% contribution of highly polar structures. Assuming that like thiourea the substituted compounds also give canonical structure with equal contributions, coordination through sulphur should result in a decrease in double bond character of C=S and an increase in double bond character of C-N bond; whereas if coordination is through nitrogen then just the opposite effect is to be expected together with the reduction in N-H frequency. The latter remains unchanged if the coordination is through sulphur.

The present communication deals with infra red absorption studies on the complexes of cuprous chloride with *s*-diphenyl thiourea (D. P. T. U.), naphthyl thiourea (N. T. U.), benzyl thiourea hydrochloride (B. T. U.), allyl thiourea (A. T. U.), diisopropyl thiourea (D. I. P. T. U.) and *o*-tolyl thiourea (T. T. U.)

EXPERIMENTAL

A. T. U. and D. I. P. T. U. (E. Merck products); N. T. U., D. P. T. U., and T. T. U. (B. D. H. products) and B. T. U. (Light products) were used during the experiments. The products were purified by crystallisation from acetone. The solutions of the reagents were prepared in acetone.

Cuprous chloride was prepared by the method recommended by Keller and Wycoff⁶. Solutions of cuprous chloride were prepared in concentrated KCl.

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The infra red spectra were recorded with a Beckman IR-5 spectrophotometer using NaCl prism and Nujol mull films. The apparatus was checked by polystyrene films and carbon tetrachloride.

The magnetic susceptibility measurements were performed with Gouy magnetic balance.

Preparation of the Complexes: Bis (D. P. T. U.) Cu (I) Chloride. About 35 ml. of D. P. T. U. (0.01M soln. in acetone) were added to about 15 ml (0.01M) of Cuprous chloride (in 2M KCl). The whole mixture was refluxed for 30-45 mts. over a water bath. The white product which settled down, was separated and filtered through a sintered funnel and it was washed several times with water and small aliquots of acetone to remove potassium chloride and excess of complexing reagent respectively. The whole mixture was then transferred to a flask and about 100 ml. of acetone were added to it. The mixture was heated over a water bath for about 20 mins. The hot reaction mixture was passed through filter paper and the light coloured filtrate was kept for crystallization in a vacuum desiccator when the crystals of the product appeared after a few days.

Light yellowish brown crystals: m.p. 140°, Anal. Calc. for $C_{26}H_{24}N_4S_2$ CuCl, C-56.1, H-4.3, N-10.0, S-11.5, Cu-11.5, Cl-6.4. Found: C*-53.3, H-4.6, N-9.4, S-11.1, Cu-11.3, Cl-6.3. The preparation of the complexes with other substituted thioureas were carried out more or less by the same procedure as described in case of D. P. T. U. complex. Bis (N.T.U.) Cu (I) chloride: Dirty yellow crystals, m.p. 225-226°. Anal. Calc. for $C_{22}H_{20}N_4S_2$ CuCl, C-52.5, H-3.9, N-11.1, S-12.7, Cu-22.7, Cl-7.5. Found: C*-48.3, H-3.6, N-11.1, S-13.0, Cu-12.6, Cl-7.6. Mono (T. T. U.) Cu (I) chloride: Brownish black product, m.p. 300°. Anal. Calc. for $C_8H_{10}N_2S$ CuCl, C-36.2, H-3.8, N-10.6, S-12.1, Cu-24.0, Cl-13.4. Found: C*-34.3, H-3.7, N-10.5, S-12.1, Cu-23.8, Cl-13.2. Bis (D.I.P.T.U.) Cu (I) Chloride: Light yellow crystals, m.p. 265°. Anal. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{32}N_4S_2$ CuCl, C-40.1, H-7.6, N-13.3, S-15.3, Cu-15.1, Cl-8.5. Found: C-40.9, H-8.4, N-13.1, S-15.3, Cu-15.2, Cl-8.4. Mono (B.T.U.) Cu(I) Chloride: Brownish product, m.p. 300°. Anal. Calc. for $C_8H_{11}N_2S$ CuCl₂, C-31.8, H-3.6, N-9.0, S-10.1, Cu-21.1, Cl-23.5. Found: C*-30.9, H-4.3, N-9.2, S-10.3, Cu-21.0, Cl-22.8. Mono (A. T. U.) Cu (I) Chloride: Yellowish white crystals, m.p. 215°. Anal. Calc. for $C_4H_6N_2S$ CuCl, C-22.2, H-3.7, N-13.0, S-14.8, Cu-29.5, Cl-16.5. Found: C-21.3, H-3.7, N-12.0, S-14.2, Cu-29.5, Cl-16.5.

The low percentage of carbon may be due to incomplete fusion of the complex. C,H,N, analysis were carried out by Australian Microanalytical Service, University of Melbourne, Melbourne. Cu was estimated iodometrically whereas chlorine was determined as AgCl.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Cuprous chloride forms complexes with D. P. T. U., D. I. P. T. U., N. T. U. (1:2), A. T. U., B. T. U. and T. T. U. (1:1). The complexes are very stable at room temperature, soluble in acetone and insoluble in water and ethanol.

All the complexes were found to be diamagnetic. The infra red spectra of substituted thioureas and the respective Cu(I) complexes were studied, in the region from 5.0 to

15.0 μ . Substituted thioureas showed strong bands near 1600 cm^{-1} which are assigned to NH_2 bending modes. The bands remain unaltered on coordination except D. I. P. T. U. and D. P. T. U. and their complexes. The ligands do not show any band in this region due to the absence of NH_2 groups. The strong band, at 1630 cm^{-1} for A.T.U. may be assigned to $\text{C}=\text{C}$ stretching and deformation vibrations which remains unaffected on coordination (Abbreviations used: s-strong, w-weak, m-medium, b-broad)

D.I.P.T.U.	D.P.T.U.	T.T.U.	N.T.U.	B.T.U.	A.T.U.
—	—	1610(s)	1630(s)	1650(s)	1630(s)
Complex	complex	complex	complex	complex	complex
—	—	1610(s)	1630(s)	1650(s)	1630(s)

The infra red absorption bands observed near 1550 cm^{-1} are assigned to N-H deformation and C-N antisymmetric stretching vibrations. In case of D. P. T. U. there is an increase in frequency to 20 cm^{-1} whereas in all other cases (save A. T. U.) the bands remain unshifted on coordination showing thereby the presence of uncoordinated nitrogen. The absorption band of A. T. U. observed at about 1540 cm^{-1} disappears on complexation indicating thereby coordination through nitrogen.

D.I.P.T.U.	D.P.T.U.	T.T.U.	N.T.U.	B.T.U.	A.T.U.
1520(w)	1560(s)	1520(w)	1520(w)	1550(m)	1540(s)
1550(m)		1540 (w)		1560(s)	
Complex	Complex	Complex	Complex	Complex	Complex
1520(w)	1580(s)	1520(w)	1520(w)	1550(m)	—
1560(s)		1560(s)		1560(s)	

Except A. T. U. all substituted thioureas show weak bands near 1000 cm^{-1} which are assigned to symmetric C-N and NH_2 rocking vibrations. The two strong bands in D.I.P.T.U. at 1120 cm^{-1} and 1165 cm^{-1} are assigned to isopropyl skeletal vibrations, the bands remain unaffected on coordination.

Irving et al³ attributed the bands near 750 cm^{-1} as C-S stretching with small contribution of symmetric C-N stretching vibrations. Substituted thioureas also show similar behaviour on complexation. In all cases where bonding through S is inferred on the basis of the observed effect in the $1500\text{-}1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region, there is a decrease in frequency showing thereby the weakening of double bond character of C-S. In case of allyl thiourea there is a marked increase in frequency indicating the strengthening of double bond character of C-S.

D.I.P.T.U.	D.P.T.U.	T.T.U.	N.T.U.	B.T.U.	A.T.U.
750(s)	760(s)	760(s)	775(s)	750-775 (b & m)	740(s)
Complex	Complex	Complex	Complex	Complex	Complex
745(s)	745(s)	715(s)	765(s)	770(s)	765(s)

From the foregoing discussion it may be concluded that in all cases except that of A.T.U. there is coordination through sulphur whereas in case of A. T. U. the presence of a N-M bond cannot be ruled out.

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